

Understanding the Gateway: Unpacking the Mechanisms, Boundaries, and Outcomes of Climate Consensus Messaging

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Abstract

Communicating the scientific consensus on climate change acts as a gateway to increasing climate beliefs, a process described by the Gateway Belief Model (GBM). Although the effectiveness of this approach is well-documented, critical gaps in the literature persist. Few studies have scrutinized the risks of low-consensus messages and their correctability, the potential for consensus messaging to have an impact beyond self-reported measures, or the cognitive mechanisms driving belief updates. This study addresses these three critical areas in a German sample ($N = 941$). First, we demonstrate the powerful adverse effect of a low-consensus message on the perceived scientific consensus (PSC) and show that this effect can be corrected through subsequent accurate messaging. Second, we introduce learning as a novel cognitive outcome, finding that high-consensus messaging can act as a gateway to knowledge acquisition. Third, we explore key psychological moderators, revealing that while initial confidence can influence belief updating under certain conditions, psychological reactance does not inhibit PSC change. Crucially, we find no evidence of an increased reactance as a result of consensus messaging (“backfire effect”), confirming that consensus messaging is a robust and low-risk communication tool.

Keywords:

- Gateway Belief Model
- Climate Consensus Messaging
- Psychological Reactance
- Climate Education
- Climate Change

1. Introduction

The consequences of climate change are profound and pervasive, ranging from ecological disruption, such as extreme weather and biodiversity loss (Rawat et al., 2023), to deteriorating public and mental health (Cianconi et al., 2020). Yet, progress on this crisis is fundamentally constrained by psychological barriers (Steg, 2023). Key barriers include public skepticism and a diminished sense of urgency (Hornsey et al., 2016; van der Linden et al., 2015). The resulting passivity impedes the implementation of vital technical and policy solutions, magnifying the long-term risks and costs of climate impacts.

1.1. Overcoming Psychological Barriers through Consensus Messaging

To overcome these barriers, psychological models seek to understand climate belief formation and increase public engagement (Spence et al., 2012; Steg, 2023). A prominent example is the Gateway Belief Model (GBM), which leverages the "consensus implies correctness" heuristic (Darke et al., 1998). The model posits that communicating high expert agreement on anthropogenic climate change serves as a *gateway* that updates an individual's perception of the scientific consensus. This, in turn, is hypothesized to produce a cascading effect, strengthening beliefs about climate change's existence, human causation, and worry, and finally increasing support for public action (van der Linden et al., 2019).

A growing body of research supports the GBM's core predictions. The most robust finding from large-scale, international studies is that consensus messaging significantly increases the perceived scientific consensus (PSC) (Stekelenburg et al., 2024; Većkalov et al., 2024; Zeng et al., 2025). This increase often cascades to strengthen beliefs about climate change's existence and human cause (Stekelenburg et al., 2024; van der Linden et al., 2019; Većkalov et al., 2024), though the evidence is less clear in populations drawn from outside of the US, such as Germany (Said et al., 2022; Tschötschel et al., 2021).

1.2. Current Gaps in the Gateway Belief Model Literature

Despite empirical support for the GBM, its literature contains critical gaps regarding underlying mechanisms, boundary conditions, and practical implications. For example, its impact beyond self-reported measures and the psychological factors moderating its effectiveness remain largely unknown. This study addresses three fundamental questions to fill these gaps.

First, what are the effects of communicating a low scientific consensus? While the impact of high-consensus messages is well-documented (Stekelenburg et al., 2024; Većkalov et al., 2024; Zeng et al., 2025), less is known about the impact of low-consensus messages. Examining such factually incorrect messages is informative and ecologically valid, simulating a prevalent misinformation strategy used by climate skeptics (Meah, 2019). Furthermore, investigating the impact of such a message is crucial for understanding if it merely fails to persuade individuals or even triggers an opposing heuristic, where disagreement implies expert division. A few studies have investigated the impact of low-consensus messages and found that they lead to significant PSC decreases (Kerr & van der Linden, 2022; Kerr & Wilson, 2018).

However, these effects have not yet been tested in a GBM context in Germany, where the PSC regarding anthropogenic climate change is high and where a large proportion of the population reports exposure to disinformation (Reuter et al., 2022; Said et al., 2023). We aim to fill this gap by testing the impact of a low-consensus message (55%) versus a high-consensus message (97%). We hypothesize that the low-consensus message will decrease PSC, while the high-consensus message will increase it (H1).

Additionally, to assess the message's strength and inform mitigation strategies, we investigate whether the adverse effects of low-consensus communication can be reversed

through debriefing. In a high-consensus population like Germany, a low-consensus message could trigger the aforementioned disagreement heuristic. However, because such a message misaligns with individuals' prior assumptions, the belief in it might be low. According to Kunda's (1990) theory of motivated reasoning, the drive to defend such a weak, counter-normative belief is low, allowing a more plausible and causally coherent alternative (97% consensus) to effectively overwrite the initial message during debriefing. We therefore hypothesize that the adverse effects of the low-consensus message can be overwritten by providing participants in the low-consensus group with a high-consensus message (97%) in a debriefing, elevating their consensus level to that of the high-consensus group (H2).

Second, do the effects of consensus messaging extend beyond self-reported beliefs to more tangible cognitive outcomes, such as knowledge acquisition? The GBM literature has almost exclusively relied on self-report measures (Said et al., 2022; van der Linden et al., 2019; Zeng et al., 2025). However, individuals do not always act according to their self-reported attitudes (Ajzen, 1991). Furthermore, one of the few studies testing the influence of consensus messaging on actual behavior, in this case, donation behavior, in the context of climate change, found no such influence (Deryugina & Shurchkov, 2016). To address this gap, we focused on whether updated consensus beliefs influence subsequent information processing. For instance, as a high-consensus message plays on the consensus implies correctness heuristic, it could be assumed that this heuristic enhances expert source credibility, which subsequently carries over to systematic processing of additional information on climate change (Petty & Cacioppo, 1986; van der Linden et al., 2019). To test this assumption, we provided our participants with an educational video on climate tipping points after the consensus manipulation and measured their learning.

We propose two hypotheses regarding learning. First, we expect a main effect of the educational content, predicting that participants' knowledge will increase after watching the

video (H3). Second, we hypothesize that the amount of learning will be moderated by the consensus message (H4), with participants in the high-consensus group learning the most and participants in the low-consensus group learning the least, compared to a control group.

Finally, to understand how learning fits within the model's established pathway, we exploratively tested a Bayesian serial mediation model. Here, we wanted to test whether our intervention would influence learning indirectly by first altering the PSC, which in turn would shape climate beliefs and ultimately impact learning.

Third, what mechanisms and psychological factors influence the effectiveness of consensus messaging? For the GBM to transition from a robust theoretical framework to an effective science communication tool, its key moderators, determining its effectiveness, need to be better understood. We propose and test two potential moderators, one cognitive (the confidence in one's initial PSC) and one motivational moderator (psychological reactance).

The first moderator, confidence, could serve as a proxy for attitude strength, because one's confidence in the correctness and one's understanding of an attitude object defines attitude certainty. Attitude certainty, on the other hand, influences the strength with which an attitude is held, and weak attitudes are more susceptible to change than strong ones (Howe & Krosnick, 2017). We extend this principle to the GBM, arguing that individuals with low confidence in their initial PSC hold a weaker belief and should thus be more receptive to updating it. Previous research found that lower confidence was associated with more PSC updating after receiving a high-consensus message and found that the confidence in the updated PSC moderated climate belief updating (Said et al., 2023). Our study focuses on initial confidence since we assume that it is a more unbiased proxy for attitude certainty than post-treatment confidence. We hypothesize that initial confidence will moderate the impact of the experimental groups on PSC updating (H5a) and climate belief change (H5b), with a bigger impact in the high- and low-consensus groups and no impact in the control group

because of the absence of a consensus message to validate one's estimation of the PSC against. Furthermore, we hypothesize that across our experimental groups, lower initial confidence will predict greater PSC (H5c) and subsequent climate belief (H5d) updating. We also tested this principle in the debriefing phase, hypothesizing that low-confidence participants will show the greatest belief change when given corrective information (H6).

The second moderator, psychological reactance, is a fundamental motivational response to perceived threats on one's freedom of thought (Brehm, 1966). Its role in the GBM is contested; some find it as an undesirable side effect of consensus messaging (Chinn & Hart, 2023; Ma et al., 2019), while others find no such effect (van der Linden et al., 2023). However, while reactance was investigated as an outcome, its role as a moderator is unclear. We address this gap by testing reactance as a key moderator. Similar to prior work, we hypothesize a negative relationship between psychological reactance and the strength of pro-climate beliefs (H7) and expect reactance to be higher among those affiliated with climate-skeptical parties (H8) in our German sample. Furthermore, we hypothesize that higher psychological reactance would be associated with smaller positive changes in PSC (H9a) and climate beliefs (H9b). Finally, we exploratively test for an interaction between message type and reactance. We hypothesize that high reactance will diminish the positive persuasive impact of the prescriptive high-consensus (97%) message. Conversely, we expect this dampening effect of reactance to be weaker for the less pressuring, low-consensus (55%) message.

In summary, we address three key gaps in the GBM literature. First, we causally test the effects of both high- and low-consensus information on the PSC, which requires contrasting these messages against a baseline control condition. Second, we introduce a more tangible outcome measure by evaluating how these consensus messages impact learning from a subsequent educational video. Third, we systematically investigate the moderating roles of

confidence and psychological reactance. By pursuing these objectives, we move beyond the question of whether the GBM works to a more critical understanding of how, why, and to what extent it is effective in shaping the psychological foundations for climate engagement.

2. Method

To achieve the aforementioned objectives, we conducted a preregistered (<https://osf.io/wybgk>), three-group, between-subjects online experiment. The study received ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the Leibniz-Institut für Wissensmedien and was classified as ethically defensible (LEK 2024/044). The data and analysis scripts are available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16994001>).

2.1. Participants

We aimed for a sample of 1000 participants (approximately 333 per condition). This target, based on a preregistered a priori power analysis (G*Power; Faul et al., 2009), indicated excellent power ($>.90$) to detect small interaction effects ($f = 0.10$) at $\alpha = .05$ in repeated-measures ANOVA. Data was collected via Bilendi, which recruited a sample intended to be representative of the German population using interlocking quotas for age and gender. Before reaching our 1000 participant goal, we had to exclude 515 participants for submitting duplicate entries, participating from outside of Germany, or not meeting quota requirements. Furthermore, 59 participants were actively excluded from our final 1000 participant sample, before analysis, as they did not pass the attention check or studied psychology (a preregistered exclusion criterion). The final sample, therefore, included $N = 941$ participants ($N_{female} = 480$, $N_{male} = 461$, $M_{age} = 50.81$ years, $SD = 16.75$) who were diverse in political affiliation and educational attainment (see appendix, Table A6). Participants were randomly assigned to one of the three experimental conditions (high scientific consensus message (97%, $N = 322$), low scientific consensus message (55%, $N = 315$), and control ($N = 304$)).

2.2. Materials and Stimuli

2.2.1. Educational Video

Participants were shown a 5-minute video about climate tipping points, conditions that lead to irreversible man-made global warming, and which are a serious concern in the context of climate change (Lenton et al., 2008). We specifically selected a video as a medium because videos are particularly effective for communicating complex and dynamic processes (Ploetzner et al., 2020), such as those underlying climate change. According to the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning, understanding is enhanced when information is presented both visually and auditorily, as this facilitates the construction of coherent mental models (Mayer, 2014).

The selected video, produced by the non-profit organization KLIMA° vor acht e.V. (2021), was specifically chosen because of its alignment with these principles of learning. It combines clear narration with illustrative animations of the Greenland ice sheet melting. Its brevity and focus on essential information help to avoid extraneous cognitive load (see coherence principle; Mayer & Fiorella, 2014), thereby enabling effective learning about the complex topic.

2.2.2. Video Knowledge Test

We created a 20-item (true/false) knowledge test based on the educational video. An initial item pool was generated from the video's transcript using ChatGPT 4o (OpenAI et al., 2024) and then manually curated to ensure content validity, balanced difficulty (10 true/10 false), and clarity (no negations). The internal consistency of the knowledge test was acceptable at both pre-test ($\alpha = .71$) and post-test ($\alpha = .74$).

2.2.3. Perceived Scientific Consensus & Confidence

Following van der Linden (2015), we asked participants: "To your knowledge, what percentage of all climate researchers are of the opinion that human-made global warming is taking place?". Participants were then able to enter their answer from 0 to 100 percent using a slider. We also used a second slider scale from 50 to 100 percent to record how confident they were in their answer (see Said et al., 2023).

2.2.4. Climate Beliefs

To capture climate beliefs, participants expressed agreement regarding four key aspects on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = *low agreement* and 7 = *high agreement*): belief in climate change, human causation, their level of worry, and their support for mitigation. The items were based on van der Linden et al. (2019) and were translated into German. To create a single robust measure of climate beliefs, we created the *Overall Climate Belief Score* (OCBS). This composite score provides a more reliable measure of one's general stance on climate change compared to the single items alone ($\alpha_{pre} = .91$; $\alpha_{post} = .91$). The full questions can be found in the appendix (Table A1).

2.2.5. Reactance

Reactance was recorded as the mean of a 3-item scale based on the research of Ma et al. (2019). The adapted items were translated into German and measured on a 7-point Likert scale (ranging from 1 = *fully disagree* to 7 = *fully agree*). The original statements of the items were: "I feel pressured to have a certain opinion on climate change", "I feel that others are trying to force their opinion on climate change on me", and "I think that people are trying to manipulate my views on climate change". The internal consistency of our scale was excellent ($\alpha = .94$) and matched the reliability of the psychological reactance scale from Ma and colleagues.

2.3. Procedure

The experiment was conducted using the survey platform SoSci Survey (Leiner, 2024). Participants were initially informed that the study involved answering questions about climate change and watching a video. First, participants reported their climate beliefs (OCBS), perceived scientific consensus (PSC), and completed a pre-knowledge-test. Following this initial assessment, they were randomly assigned to one of three groups. The high-consensus group was presented with the statement, “97% of climate scientists agree that human-caused global warming is happening” (van der Linden et al., 2015), while the low-consensus group was presented with, “55% of climate scientists are of the opinion that human-caused global warming is happening” to simulate uncertainty¹. To enhance credibility, both experimental groups were told their statement was randomly selected from a large database. The consensus information was presented as both text (in German) and a visual pie chart. The control group received no consensus message and proceeded directly from the knowledge pre-test to the next step.

Immediately after the intervention, all participants viewed an educational video about climate tipping points. An attention check followed, where participants were asked if the word *Eisbär* (polar bear) appeared in the video (it did not) to verify attentive viewing. Subsequently, participants’ reactance, OCBS, climate knowledge (post-test), and PSC were measured again. At the conclusion of the experiment, participants reported demographic information, and all participants were fully debriefed about the study’s manipulation. The low-consensus group received an additional debriefing that presented the accurate scientific consensus, after which their PSC was measured a final time to assess the efficacy of the debriefing.

¹ We specifically selected 55% as a symmetrical counterpart to the 97% high-consensus value, ensuring both were equidistant from the 76% average perceived consensus found in a representative German sample (Said et al., 2022).

2.4. Data Analysis

We preregistered a frequentist analysis plan. An assumption check prior to the data analysis based on visual inspections and a Shapiro-Wilk test revealed, however, that the PSC scores violated normality across groups and timepoints (all $ps < .001$). One reason for this was the relatively high average PSC in our sample across groups ($M_{\text{pre-treatment}} = 76.56$, $SD_{\text{pre-treatment}} = 20.23$), leading to a ceiling effect and negatively skewed distributions. Additionally, Levene's test for homogeneity of variances was conducted for both timepoints and indicated violations of the homogeneity of variances at both timepoints (for PSC; T1, $p = .036$; T2, $p < .001$).

To ensure the reliability and robustness of our results, we adopted a Bayesian analytical framework for all our hypothesis tests. We chose this approach because the Bayesian methods rely less on distributional assumptions and allow a more nuanced interpretation of our results by quantifying the evidence for an alternative hypothesis over the null hypothesis through the calculation of a Bayes factor (Kass & Raftery, 1995).

Furthermore, to increase the robustness and statistical power of our analyses, all ANOVA models were fitted as Bayesian multilevel regressions using the brms package (v. 2.22.0; Bürkner, 2017) in R (v. 4.4.2). Our primary outcome variables (PSC, OCBS and Video Knowledge) were scaled between 0 and 1, so we could use a Beta response distribution, which is appropriate for modeling skewed data. Age, gender and education were included as covariates in all models.² To account for the repeated-measures nature of the data, all models included a random intercept for participant ID.

² Including education as a covariate required excluding ten participants who selected the *other qualifications* category. A sensitivity analysis confirmed the importance of the covariates. Their omission altered the conclusions for several hypotheses (H4, H5a-d, H9b,d), reinforcing the robustness of the primary, pre-specified model, including the mentioned covariates (see Appendix, Table A7).

We used weakly informative priors across all models to achieve reasonable estimates and not influence the posterior distributions too much. All models converged with sufficient R-hat values (< 1.01) and had adequate effective sample sizes. The posterior predictive checks indicated good model fit.

3. Results

3.1. Effect of (Low-)Consensus Messaging on Perceived Scientific Consensus

Our first hypothesis (H1) predicted that the change in PSC would differ across the three experimental groups. A Bayesian regression model predicting participants' PSC score depending on the timepoint (pre vs. post) confirmed this, revealing decisive evidence for a model including the predicted timepoint and group interaction ($BF_{10} > 100$). This indicates that the consensus messages altered the perceptions of the participants differently (see Figure 1). As predicted, participants in the low-consensus group showed a credible decrease in their PSC of roughly 16 percentage points on average ($M = -0.16$, 95% CI $[-0.18, -0.14]$). Conversely, the high-consensus group showed a credible mean increase of roughly 9 percentage points ($M = 0.09$, 95% CI $[0.08, 0.11]$). Interestingly, the control group, which viewed only the educational video and received no consensus message, also showed a small but credible mean increase of roughly three percentage points ($M = 0.03$, 95% CI $[0.02, 0.05]$).

Fig. 1. Change in Perceived Scientific Consensus by Groups.

Note. The change score is the difference between post- and pre-consensus message Perceived Scientific Consensus. Error bars represent the 95% confidence interval.

Furthermore, we examined whether the low-consensus-message group's perception could be corrected through debriefing (H2). After being shown the accurate 97% consensus information at the end of our experiment (T3), the average PSC of the low-consensus group increased substantially from 61% ($M = 0.61$, 95% CI [0.58, 0.64]) to 85% ($M = 0.85$, 95% CI [0.83, 0.87]) at T3 (see Figure 2). The analysis provided overwhelming evidence for this increase ($M_{\Delta} = 0.24$, 95% CI [0.22, 0.27]; $BF_{10} > 100$). The average PSC of the high-consensus group after receiving the consensus message (T2) was 88% (95% CI [0.86, 0.90]). A Bayesian independent sample t-test provided strong evidence for no meaningful difference between the PSC levels of the low-consensus group at T3 and the high-consensus group at T2 ($BF_{10} = 0.09$), supporting H2.

Fig. 2. Average Perceived Scientific Consensus at Different Time Points for the “low” Group. *Note.* Error bars represent the 95% confidence interval.

3.2. Effect of Consensus Messaging on Learning

We hypothesized that viewing the educational climate tipping point video would increase climate knowledge (H3) and that this learning effect would be influenced by the consensus message condition (H4).

Our third hypothesis of an overall learning effect received mixed support. A Bayesian paired-samples t-test provided decisive evidence for an increase in knowledge scores from T1 to T2 ($BF_{10} > 100$). However, this effect was of a small magnitude. First, the estimated marginal means indicated a credible positive knowledge increase of only 2% ($M_{pre} = 0.76$, $M_{post} = 0.78$, $M_{\Delta} = 0.02$, 95% CI [0.01, 0.03]). Second, in a comparison of a beta regression model including a time effect with a simpler null model without a time effect, the simpler model was decisively preferred ($BF_{01} > 100$). In the time model, the time coefficient was credibly positive ($\beta = 0.11$, 95% CI [0.06, 0.16]; link scale), which was not substantial enough to justify its inclusion in the model based on a Bayes factor test. Overall, these results indicate

a small knowledge increase that is less pronounced when looking at individuals' average change trajectories compared to the overall simple difference in knowledge scores pre- vs. post-treatment.

In line with our fourth hypothesis (H4), we found decisive evidence for a model that included an interaction between group and time compared to an otherwise equal model without an interaction ($BF_{10} > 100$), indicating that learning effects differed among groups (see Figure 3). However, while the overall patterns differed, the specific differences between any two groups were too uncertain to be clearly distinguished, as all 95% credible intervals for group interactions included zero (e.g., high vs. control: $\beta = -0.03$, 95% CI [-0.16, 0.09]; link scale).

Fig. 3. Mean change in Video Knowledge by Experimental Groups.

Note. Error bars represent the 95% confidence interval.

Additionally, the exploratory Bayesian mediation model, mentioned in the introduction, assessed the effect of the experimental group on the learning outcome serially

moderated by the PSC and the OCBS. All analyses controlled for participants' pre-test scores. Given our prior assumptions of differences in learning based on the type of consensus message, we specified two models to clearly delineate the effects. In the first model, we compared the high-consensus group, and in the second model, we compared the low-consensus group to the control group. Based on posterior predictive checks, our models provided a good fit for the data. The visualized models are presented in Figure 4.

In the high-consensus model, we found a credible positive total effect of the intervention on learning ($\beta = 0.23$, 95% CI [0.05, 0.41], *Post. Prob.* > .99). This was explained by a strong indirect effect, where the intervention increased learning through an increase in PSC ($\beta = 0.32$, 95% CI [0.14, 0.53], *Post. Prob.* > .99). Specifically, the high-consensus message increased the PSC ($\beta = 0.55$, 95% CI [0.43, 0.68]), which in turn predicted higher learning outcomes ($\beta = 0.59$, 95% CI [0.26, 0.91]).

There was no credible evidence for a direct effect of the intervention on learning after accounting for the influence of the mediators ($\beta = -0.08$, 95% CI [-0.19, 0.04]) or for the serial mediation path via climate beliefs, indicating that the consensus message effect in the high group on learning outcomes is entirely mediated by its impact on the PSC.

In stark contrast, the model for the low-consensus message showed no credible effects. There was no evidence for a total effect ($\beta = -0.17$, 95% CI [-0.42, 0.07]), direct effect ($\beta = 0.02$, 95% CI [-0.10, 0.14]), or an indirect effect through the PSC pathway ($\beta = -0.18$, 95% CI [-0.46, 0.09]).

Fig. 4. Bayesian Path Analysis Models of the Effect of High- (A) and Low-Consensus (B) Messaging on Learning: Mediated by the Perceived Scientific Consensus (PSC).

Note. Both models represent a small part of the larger mediation model, which included a further mediation step via climate beliefs. The reported estimates are the means of the posterior distribution on a logit scale and the values in brackets show the 95% credible interval. All paths for which the 95% credible interval did not include zero are highlighted in bold font. The c' path represents the direct effect of the consensus condition on the learning outcome after controlling for the PSC. All posterior predictive checks indicated a good model fit. $N = 626$ for A and $N = 619$ for B.

3.3. The Role of Confidence

Regarding the role of confidence, we posited two hypotheses. First, we hypothesized a direct main effect of confidence on belief updating, where lower confidence would predict greater updating for both PSC (H5a) and OCBS (H5b). Alternatively, we hypothesized that the effect of the consensus message would be moderated by initial confidence (H5c, H5d).

For PSC updating, our analysis found no evidence for either hypothesized role of initial confidence. We first tested for a general influence of confidence on PSC updating (a time and confidence interaction, H5a) and found decisive evidence against it in favor of a simpler model without the interaction ($BF_{01} > 100$). Similarly, the data provided decisive

evidence against the more complex three-way (time, group, and confidence) interaction (H5c), strongly favoring the baseline model without the moderation ($BF_{01} > 100$). Thus, for the direct updating of the PSC, initial confidence appears to play no discernible role as a moderator.

In contrast, for the updating of the OCBS, initial confidence did emerge as a meaningful moderator. While the data decisively rejected a simple time and confidence interaction model (H5b; $BF_{01} > 100$), it provided decisive evidence for a three-way interaction model (H5d; $BF_{10} > 100$), both compared to a baseline model without an interaction with confidence. This indicates that the influence of initial confidence on climate belief updating depends on the consensus group. Probing this interaction revealed subtle group differences (see Figure 5). In the low-consensus message and control group, individuals with lower confidence ($-1SD$) showed greater climate belief updating (e.g. low-consensus group: $\Delta = 0.04$, 95% CI [0.01, 0.06]) compared to those with higher initial confidence (low-consensus group, $+1SD$: $\Delta = 0.02$, 95% CI [0.00, 0.03]). In the high group, climate belief updating seemed to have been largely independent of one's initial confidence ($-1SD$: $\Delta = 0.03$, 95% CI [0.01, 0.05]; $+1SD$: $\Delta = 0.03$, 95% CI [0.01, 0.04]). Despite this clear pattern, the posterior estimates for the key three-way interaction parameters were uncertain and their credible intervals included zero (e.g., for the high-consensus group vs. control: $\beta = 0.08$, 95% CI [-0.05, 0.21]), reflecting high data variability. Consequently, we cannot be certain about the magnitude and direction of the three-way interaction.

Fig. 5. Moderation of Climate Belief Updating by Initial Confidence and Experimental Group. *Note.* Predicted climate beliefs based on the Bayesian mixed-effects model for H5d. Scores range from 0 to 1 (highest possible belief score). Black lines represent the mean posterior prediction for pre-treatment scores (T1), and dark green lines represent the post-treatment prediction (T2). The areas around the lines indicate the 95% credible intervals around the predictions. Each panel shows the connection between initial confidence and climate belief updating for a different experimental group.

Furthermore, we investigated whether the PSC updating in the low-consensus group after receiving the debriefing message was moderated by the initial confidence of participants (H6). The analysis yielded very strong evidence for an interaction ($BF_{10} = 67.32$). The negative interaction coefficient ($\beta = -0.28$, 95% CI [-0.42, -0.13]) indicates that participants with lower prior confidence showed a larger positive update in their PSC scores after being debriefed (see Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Association Between Initial Confidence and Change in PSC After Debriefing for the Low-Consensus Group.

Note. The scatterplot illustrates the relationship between participants' pre-treatment confidence in their Perceived Scientific Consensus (PSC) score and the subsequent change in their PSC score after debriefing (calculated as the score at Time 3 (debriefing) minus the score at Time 2 (post-treatment)). Each point represents an individual participant. The solid black line is the linear regression line of best fit, with the surrounding shaded area representing the 95% confidence interval.

3.4. The role of Reactance

Regarding the role of psychological reactance, we first confirmed a strong link between pre-treatment climate beliefs and reactance (H7). A Bayesian regression revealed decisive evidence for the inclusion of the initial OCBS in predicting reactance scores ($BF_{10} > 100$) and indicated a negative relationship, whereby participants with stronger pro-climate beliefs reported substantially lower levels of reactance ($\beta = -0.88$, 95% CI [-0.96, -0.79]) (see Figure 7).

Fig. 7. Relationship between Reactance and the Pre-Treatment Overall Climate Belief Score (OCBS). *Note.* Each semi-transparent dot represents an individual participant. The solid black line is the linear regression line of best fit, which models the overall trend. The gray shaded area represents the 95% confidence interval for the trend line.

Additionally, we confirmed that reactance varied systematically across political party affiliations (H8), with overwhelming evidence for a model including the party variable, compared to an otherwise identical model without the variable ($BF_{10} > 100$). As illustrated in Figure 8, supporters of the right-wing AfD reported the highest reactance (reactance scaled between 0 and 1, $M = 0.56$, 95% CI [0.51, 0.62]), while supporters of the Green Party reported the lowest ($M = 0.19$, 95% CI [0.16, 0.23]).

Fig. 8. Reactance by Political Party Affiliation in Germany.

Note. The width of each colored violin shape represents the estimated probability density of the data. Within each violin, the boxplot displays the median (center line), the interquartile range (the box). Each semi-transparent dot represents an individual participant. The label ('NONE') includes respondents reporting no party affiliation.

Furthermore, we tested whether higher levels of reactance are associated with less PSC (H9a) and climate belief (H9b) updating across groups. Contrary to our prediction in H9a, our analysis provided decisive evidence for an effect in the opposite direction, with higher reactance being associated with more positive PSC updating. Our findings were ambiguous for the association of reactance and climate belief updating (H9b). In both cases, a model with an interaction of reactance and time was favored over a model that did not include the interaction (H9a: $BF_{10} > 100$, H9b: $BF_{10} = 8.79$).

Our further explorative analysis, for which we considered a three-way interaction effect, including time, group, and reactance, predicting the PSC and climate beliefs, revealed

an interesting pattern. Compared to the reactance models with only a two-way interaction of reactance and time, a Bayes factor test revealed decisive evidence for the three-way interaction model predicting the PSC ($BF_{10} > 100$) and decisive evidence against the model predicting climate beliefs ($BF_{01} > 100$). This indicated that the three-way interaction model better explained our data for the PSC prediction, while the simpler two-way interaction seemed to be the superior model for the climate belief prediction. We therefore decided to interpret those models.

The posterior estimate of the 95% credible interval for the climate beliefs model for the two-way reactance and timepoint interaction term was found to include zero ($\beta = -0.04$, 95% CI [-0.09, 0.02]). This suggests that while the data might be better explained through a two-way interaction when predicting climate beliefs, the interaction effect might be small and uncertain overall.

In contrast, the posterior estimates for the three-way interaction model predicting the PSC, while not including zero, revealed a counterintuitive pattern. The interaction pattern indicated that higher reactance amplified PSC change in response to both low- and high-consensus messages. However, we suspected this pattern could be a statistical artifact, such as a ceiling effect, given that participants' initial high PSC levels could constrain their potential for change.

To test this assumption, we conducted a more robust follow-up analysis. Similar to Said et al. (2023), we calculated relative change scores, considering participants' initial distance from the message (e.g., 97%). For our robust analysis, we used a Bayesian regression with a Student's t-distribution to account for the influence of extreme outliers (participants for whom the PSC moved further away from the target).

$$RelativeChangeScore = \frac{|Consensus\ Value - PSC1| - |Consensus\ Value - PSC2|}{|Consensus\ Value - PSC1|}$$

This more robust analysis revealed a different story. After accounting for participants' room for change, the counterintuitive effects of reactance vanished. For both the high-consensus group ($\beta = -0.00$, 95% CI [-0.01, 0.01]) and the low-consensus group ($\beta = -0.05$, 95% CI [-0.11, 0.00]), there was no longer a credible effect of reactance on PSC updating. This provides us with solid evidence for the assumption that the patterns observed in the initial interaction model were a statistical artifact and that psychological reactance was not systematically related to the PSC change in our experiment.

Finally, exploratively testing for increased reactance as an outcome of consensus messaging (“backfire effect”), our analysis revealed that there was no evident difference between the reactance scores of the three experimental groups (Figure 9; a Bayesian ANOVA provided moderate evidence for the null hypothesis, $BF_{01} = 3.67$). This finding also held for specific subgroups, in which, based on the previous literature (Ma et al., 2019), a backfire effect could have been expected. Among AfD and FDP voters (who had the highest average reactance levels in our sample), the data provided anecdotal evidence for a null model assuming no difference in reactance levels between experimental groups for this subgroup ($BF_{01} = 1.39$). For a model only considering those individuals with OCBS values one standard deviation below the mean of this score, our analysis again provided anecdotal evidence for a null model, suggesting no reactance difference among groups ($BF_{01} = 2.56$).

Fig. 9. Distribution of Reactance Scores by Group.

Note. The plot includes data from all participants. Each semi-transparent dot represents an individual participant. The line within each box represents the median score, and the box itself indicates the interquartile range. The diamond in each bar indicates the mean reactance score for this group. The error bars around the diamond indicate the 95% confidence interval.

4. Discussion

Our study addressed three key gaps in the Gateway Belief Model (GBM) literature: the lack of evidence regarding the impact of low-consensus messages in Germany, the uncertain effectiveness of the GBM beyond self-reported beliefs, and the role of two potential moderators (confidence and reactance) for belief updating. First, we showed that in a German population with high climate change awareness, a single low-consensus message (55%) significantly decreased the perceived scientific consensus (PSC). Second, we found that effective consensus messaging promotes knowledge acquisition in climate science by increasing PSC. Although our data suggested a different learning trajectory between our experimental groups, the evidence for this interaction was not conclusive, and we observed no adverse effect of the low-consensus message on learning. Third, we explored initial

confidence and psychological reactance as potential moderators for belief updating. Initial confidence in PSC did not impact the direct updating of PSC estimates, but it did moderate PSC correction after a debriefing, whereas lower confidence was associated with more PSC updating. While higher reactance was associated with more PSC updating, this appeared to be a statistical artifact. Finally, exploratory analyses showed no evidence that high-consensus messaging induced psychological reactance, even among climate-skeptical participants.

4.1. The Negative Effect of a Low-Consensus Message

We found that a low-consensus message adversely affects PSC, aligning with previous research (Kerr & van der Linden, 2022; Kerr & Wilson, 2018). Notably, in our German sample, the consensus messages had an asymmetric influence. While the low-consensus message led to an average decrease in the PSC of 16 percentage points, the high-consensus message yielded only a nine percentage points increase. This could be due to a ceiling effect, given the high average baseline PSC. Alternatively, a negativity bias may make the uncertainty and doubt introduced by the low-consensus message more salient than being informed of agreement through the high-consensus message (a positive message) (Baumeister et al., 2001).

Furthermore, manufacturing doubt is a known strategy used to undermine public trust in science (Oreskes & Conway, 2010), and our study provides empirical evidence for the effectiveness of such a strategy through a low-consensus message. The effectiveness of just a single message highlights a significant vulnerability, especially in the current times, in which individuals are increasingly confronted with disinformation (Reuter et al., 2022). This clearly indicates the need for future research investigating whether the reduction in PSC translates to other negative outcomes, such as decreased trust in science and reduced support for climate policies.

In a more optimistic light, our study provided evidence for the possibility of overwriting the adverse effects of the low-consensus message through providing a high 97% consensus message in a debriefing. Providing individuals in our low-consensus group with a high-consensus message elevated their group's PSC level to a level statistically indistinguishable from that of the high-consensus group. Especially for participants with lower initial confidence in their PSC, the debriefing was effective in countering the adverse effects of the low-consensus message. These findings underscore the importance of accurate consensus messaging as a corrective tool for countering disinformation.

4.2. Consensus Messaging as a Gateway to Learning

A primary contribution of our study is extending the GBM to learning, a key cognitive outcome beyond self-reported beliefs. Our findings revealed that a high-consensus message can enhance knowledge acquisition, and this process works through the mechanisms that the GBM postulates. The effect of the high-consensus message on learning was fully mediated by participants' perceived scientific consensus. One explanation for this might be that the consensus message acted as a powerful heuristic cue that increased the perceived credibility of the scientific source, which in turn could have led to a deeper engagement with the educational video content (Petty & Cacioppo, 1986).

Regarding the low-consensus group, the low-consensus message did not negatively affect learning. This null effect could be because the professional quality of the educational video itself acted as a credibility cue, or because high baseline knowledge left little room for suppressive effects. Overall, these findings suggest that while high-consensus messaging might be a key in unlocking learning on relevant climate science topics, a low-consensus message expressing uncertainty might not be a barrier in itself for learning.

4.3. The Nuanced Role of Confidence

Our results revealed a nuanced interplay between pre-existing confidence and receptiveness to consensus messaging, where the effect of initial confidence appeared contingent on the message received. In the high-consensus condition, participants updated their beliefs regardless of their initial confidence. In contrast, in the low-consensus and control conditions, higher confidence was associated with less belief updating. This suggests a high-consensus message may act as a validating force for confident individuals, but without it, high confidence may function as a barrier to persuasion, reinforcing existing beliefs. This pattern should only be considered as theoretically informative, because the 95% credible intervals were wide and included zero, which means the true direction of the relationship could be different.

Unlike Said et al. (2023), we found an association between initial confidence and PSC updating only in our debriefing phase, not the main experiment. One explanation for this could be that during the experimental phase, the PSC was processed as a cold cognitive estimate. The consensus message may have functioned as a simple numerical anchor provided by a credible source (the experimenters), causing participants to adjust their estimate toward this authoritative number regardless of their initial confidence.

This dynamic shifted during the debriefing, where the focus was on belief correction. Cognitive dissonance theory (Festinger, 1957) may explain this. Faced with two conflicting consensus estimates, participants may have experienced cognitive dissonance. Those with low prior confidence in their own estimation of the scientific consensus likely discarded the less credible low estimate and updated towards the high-consensus anchor. Conversely, those with high initial confidence already possessed a strong internal anchor in the form of their initial consensus estimate. It is therefore possible that they relied more on their personal anchor, which was, on average, high but lower than the corrective 97% figure, and consequently updated less.

4.4. The Limited Role of Psychological Reactance and the Absence of a Backfire Effect

Contrary to common concerns that consensus messaging might backfire among skeptical audiences (Chinn & Hart, 2023; Ma et al., 2019), our study found little evidence for an inhibition of PSC updating through higher psychological reactance. After correcting for potential ceiling effects, PSC updating across groups appeared independent of reactance, suggesting the role of reactance as a barrier in this context may be negligible.

Our results suggested a potential relationship between reactance and climate belief updating that was independent of the type of consensus message received. The parameter estimate indicated that individuals with higher reactance tended to update their climate beliefs less, regardless of their experimental group. However, this evidence was statistically uncertain, as the 95% credible interval was wide and included zero. While this finding is plausible, as higher reactance correlated with lower initial climate beliefs and support for climate-skeptical parties, it should be interpreted with caution. Crucially, because this uncertain effect was independent of the experimental condition, it suggests that high-consensus messaging does not exacerbate resistance among those who are already skeptical. This supports the view that consensus messaging is a low-risk climate communication strategy.

4.5. Limitations and Future Directions

The findings of this study should be considered in light of several limitations. First, while our debriefing successfully corrected the negative effect of the low-consensus message, the effectiveness of this one-shot correction needs to be viewed with caution. In a noisy, real-world scenario, a single correction competes against repeated exposure to misinformation, which can have a continued influence on beliefs even after being corrected (Lewandowsky et

al., 2012). A longitudinal design is needed to confirm that this corrective effect persists over time and is not merely a short-lived artifact of an experimental setting.

Second, although we found a clear mediation path from the consensus message to learning, the overall learning effect was small, and the evidence for different learning trajectories between groups was ambiguous. This may be due to a ceiling effect, as our sample already possessed high baseline knowledge of the facts presented. Our novel, time-efficient approach to creating knowledge items may have resulted in questions that were too simple. Moreover, the modest learning gains may also be explained by the video's content, which focused on climate tipping points rather than the scientific consensus itself. While this provides a conservative test of the message's standalone impact, the lower thematic alignment could have precluded a synergistic effect. A video directly reinforcing the consensus topic could plausibly have produced a stronger learning outcome. Future studies could test this assumption and should use a more thoroughly validated knowledge test with items challenging enough to avoid ceiling effects and allow for a greater magnitude of learning. Furthermore, future studies should test different learning materials, such as text, in the context of the GBM approach and test if the learning effects extend to different domains other than climate science.

Third, our study recorded only the final learning outcome, so we cannot make precise statements about how intensively participants engaged with the learning video. Future studies could employ methods like eye-tracking to capture cognitive engagement more directly (Miller, 2015).

Fourth, the relationship between confidence and belief updating may differ across populations. The weaker link we observed in our German sample compared to findings from the US (Said et al., 2023) warrants further cross-cultural investigation. Future research should

also explore the role of source credibility and trust as a potential link between confidence and belief updating.

Finally, our measurement timing for psychological reactance warrants consideration. To prevent the measure from influencing participant responses, reactance was assessed at the conclusion of the experiment. However, this design choice means that the experimental manipulations themselves could have influenced participants' reported reactance, potentially introducing measurement noise. This may obscure the true moderating role of participants' actual reactance in the belief-updating process. Future research could mitigate this by measuring reactance prior to the main experiment or by using implicit measures to obtain a more unbiased estimate, which could help clarify the uncertain relationship between reactance and climate belief updating.

5. Conclusion

Our study's primary contribution is demonstrating that the Gateway Belief Model extends beyond belief change to the key cognitive outcome of learning. We demonstrate that consensus messaging does not merely persuade but instead functions as a gateway to knowledge acquisition. Our findings show that strengthening the perception of scientific consensus facilitates the learning of complex climate information, possibly by fostering deeper engagement with the educational content.

This potential for consensus messages to facilitate learning of climate facts is particularly significant given our other findings, which delineate the boundaries and resilience of the consensus approach. While we confirmed the potent negative effect of a single inaccurate message, underscoring the challenge posed by such disinformation, we also demonstrated its correctability, affirming that accurate messaging is a robust tool for restoring public perception.

Our results mitigate common concerns about psychological reactance and potential backfire effects. We found that consensus messaging is a low-risk, high-reward strategy that does not alienate even skeptical audiences, solidifying its role as a foundational climate communication tool.

These findings highlight the potential for consensus messages to not only be effective in changing self-reported climate beliefs but also to extend to more tangible cognitive outcomes such as learning.

Author Contributions

Jan Pascal Göbel: Validation, Formal analysis, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Review & Editing, Visualization **Jürgen Buder:** Writing - Review & Editing **Malik Ogiermann:** Methodology, Investigation **Matana Burkhardt:** Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation **Alina Forstner:** Methodology, Investigation **Helen Fischer:** Writing - Review & Editing **Markus Huff:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition

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Data Availability Statement

The data, analysis scripts, and supplementary materials for this study are openly available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16994001>.

Declaration of Generative AI

During the preparation of this work, J. P. Göbel used Google Gemini (Version: 2.5 Pro) in order to shorten the written text to adhere to the word limit and to formulate it more clearly, ensuring improved readability. After using this tool, J. P. Göbel reviewed and edited the content and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of Interest

None.

Appendix

Table A1

Overview of Translated Items of Dependent Variables

Variable	Item (translated from German)	Response Scale (translated from German)
Support for climate measures	In your opinion, should people do more or less to slow down global warming?	1 = Much less 4 = Same as before 7 = Much more
Belief in global warming	How strongly do you believe that global warming is happening or not happening?	1 = I strongly believe that global warming is NOT HAPPENING 4 = I am unsure whether global warming is happening or not 7 = I strongly believe that global warming IS HAPPENING
Belief in human causation	Assuming global warming is happening: To what extent do you think it is caused by human activities, natural changes in the environment, or a combination of both?	1 = I believe that global warming is primarily caused by natural changes in the environment 4 = I believe that global warming is caused equally by natural changes in the environment and by human activities 7 = I believe that global warming is primarily caused by human activities
Worry about global warming	How worried are you about global warming?	1 = I am not at all worried about global warming 4 = Neutral 7 = I am very worried about global warming
Perceived Scientific Consensus (PSC)	To your knowledge, what percentage of all climate researchers are of the opinion that human-made global warming is taking place?	Continuous scale from 0% to 100% (in 1% increments)
Confidence in PSC	Please indicate how confident you are in your assessment.	Continuous scale from 50% to 100% (in 1% increments)
Reactance 1	I think that people are trying to manipulate my views on climate change.	1 = Fully disagree 4 = Neutral 7 = Fully agree
Reactance 2	I feel that others are trying to force their opinion on climate change on me.	1 = Fully disagree 4 = Neutral 7 = Fully agree
Reactance 3	I feel pressured to have a certain opinion on climate change.	1 = Fully disagree 4 = Neutral 7 = Fully agree

Note. Items for measuring the four climate change attitudes and the perceived scientific consensus were adapted from van der Linden et al. (2019). The Confidence scale was adapted from Said et al. (2023) and the Reactance scale was adapted from Ma et al. (2019).

Table A2

Overview of Knowledge Test Items (Stem) and Proportions of Correct Answers (Pre- vs. Post-Test)

Question Stem (translated from German)	Pre-Test Prop. Correct	Post-Test Prop. Correct
Greenland ice melting faster than 40 yrs ago?	85.8	89.8
Hamburg flood protection: Million € investment?	84.2	87.7
Tipping point forecast impossible (complexity)?	58.7	70.5

Greenland ice smaller in summer?	80.2	86.0
Height loss -> faster melt (warmer air)?	70.6	87.2
Low-region precipitation: Rain instead of snow?	71.2	82.8
Greenland melt: Sea level rise outlasts climate protection?	79.0	82.8
Fossil fuels main cause of CO ₂ rise?	70.1	71.8
Climate change: Arctic more habitable?	59.9	53.5
Sea level rise: Increased seismic activity?	66.0	60.1
Greenland ice melts faster winter than summer?	78.4	78.3
Precipitation (regardless if rain) prevents ice loss?	74.8	71.1
Greenland tipping point reversible by CO ₂ cuts?	83.3	86.3
Rain stops Greenland ice melt?	89.0	88.7
Greenland melt offset by snowfall?	79.2	68.3
Sea level rise reversible in few years?	85.7	84.6
Feedback Greenland/tipping points no major climate impact?	73.1	75.1
Technical flood protection permanent solution?	74.0	78.1
Greenland melt effects theoretical/unmeasurable?	72.3	69.8
Tech. protection alone offsets CO ₂ / stops ice melt?	78.7	77.0

Note. Proportions given are percentages. A proportion of 100 would indicate that every participant answered the question correctly. At the Post-Test timepoint the participants have watched a climate tipping point video that should provide them with the information to answer every question correctly.

Table A3

Overview of Full Knowledge Test Items and Correct Responses

Full Question (translated from German)	Correct Response
Is the ice in Greenland melting faster than it did 40 years ago?	Correct
Does flood protection in Hamburg already require investments amounting to millions?	Correct
Is the exact prediction of when a tipping point will be exceeded impossible due to the complexity of climate systems?	Correct
Does Greenland's ice sheet become smaller during the summer months?	Correct
Can the loss of height of the ice sheet lead to it melting faster because it reaches warmer air layers?	Correct
Can precipitation in lower regions of Greenland fall more frequently as rain instead of snow?	Correct
Could the melting of Greenland's ice over millennia lead to a sea-level rise that outlasts current climate protection measures?	Correct
Can fossil fuels like coal and oil be the main cause of rising CO ₂ emissions?	Correct
Can climate change lead to previously uninhabitable areas like the Arctic becoming more habitable?	Correct
Can a rapid rise in sea level due to the melting of ice sheets lead to a redistribution of geological mass and thus to increased seismic activity?	Correct
Does Greenland ice melt faster in winter than in summer?	False
Does precipitation in lower, warmer regions prevent ice loss, regardless of whether it falls as rain?	False
Can a tipping point reached in Greenland's ice be completely reversed by later CO ₂ reductions?	False
Can rain stop the melting of Greenland's ice?	False
Can the melting of Greenland's ice be completely offset by natural processes such as snowfall in winter?	False

Can the rise in global sea level due to the melting of Greenland's ice be reversed within a few years?	False
Are the potential feedback effects between the melting of Greenland's ice and other climate tipping points without major impacts on the climate?	False
Are technical flood protection measures a permanent solution against sea-level rise from Greenland's melt?	False
Are the consequences of Greenland ice melt on global sea level purely theoretical and not yet measurable today?	False
Can technological protection measures alone compensate for an excess of CO2 in the atmosphere and stop ice melt?	False

Note. All questions are based on the video from KLIMA° vor acht e.V. (2021). The video was transcribed, and the LLM ChatGPT 4o was prompted to generate the questions based on video statements.

Table A4

Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlations of Pre-Treatment Attitudes and PSC with Confidence Intervals

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2	3	4	5
PSC	76.56	20.23					
Worry	5.19	1.76	.47** [.42, .52]				
Climate Support	5.49	1.61	.47** [.42, .52]	.80** [.77, .82]			
Human Causation	5.11	1.70	.55** [.51, .59]	.69** [.66, .73]	.74** [.71, .77]		
Belief in Climate Change	5.77	1.56	.53** [.48, .57]	.70** [.66, .73]	.66** [.63, .70]	.64** [.60, .67]	
Video Knowledge	0.76	0.17	.39** [.33, .44]	.32** [.26, .37]	.36** [.30, .41]	.33** [.28, .39]	.42** [.37, .47]

Note. *M* and *SD* are used to represent mean and standard deviation, respectively. Values in square brackets indicate the 95% confidence interval for each correlation. The confidence interval is a plausible range of population correlations that could have caused the sample correlation (Cumming, 2014). * indicates $p < .05$. ** indicates $p < .01$.

Table A5

Descriptive Statistics for Outcome Measures by Experimental Group

Time	Measure	M (SD)		
		control (N = 304)	high (N = 322)	low (N = 315)
Pre	PSC	74.65 (21.86)	77.94 (18.86)	76.97 (19.89)

Time	Measure	M (SD)		
		control (N = 304)	high (N = 322)	low (N = 315)
Post	PSCT	77.57 (20.58)	88.04 (17.00)	62.19 (16.25)
Pre		74.97 (17.75)	76.37 (16.10)	75.12 (16.50)
Post		79.71 (16.57)	90.59 (13.55)	87.93 (14.19)
Pre	VW	0.75 (0.16)	0.75 (0.16)	0.77 (0.17)
Post		0.77 (0.16)	0.77 (0.17)	0.78 (0.17)

Note. Values in parentheses are standard deviations. PSC = Perceived Scientific Consensus; PSCT = Confidence in Perceived Scientific Consensus; VW = Video Knowledge.

Table A6

Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

Characteristic	<i>n</i>	Percent (%) or <i>M (SD)</i>
Political Ideology	941	3.08 (0.92)
Party Affiliation		
CDU/CSU	179	19.0
SPD	160	17.0
Alliance 90/The Greens	141	15.0
AfD	141	15.0
The Left (Die Linke)	56	6.0
FDP	56	6.0
None / Other	207	22.0
Highest Level of Education		
University degree	328	34.9
Intermediate secondary	298	31.7
High school diploma (Abitur)	206	21.9
Basic secondary	97	10.3
Other qualifications	10	1.1
No formal qualification	2	0.2

Note. Total sample size is $N = 941$. Percentages may not sum to 100 due to rounding. Political ideology was assessed on a 5-point scale (1 = *very conservative*; 5 = *very liberal*). German educational qualifications were categorized as Basic secondary (Hauptschulabschluss), Intermediate secondary (Mittlerer Schulabschluss/Realschulabschluss), and High school diploma (Abitur).

A7. Sensitivity Analysis

Table A7 shows the results of our sensitivity analysis conducted to assess the robustness of the main findings to the exclusion of the pre-specified covariates (age, gender, education, and ideology for the confidence analysis in H5). This analysis serves as a critical check on our primary model specification.

As the table illustrates, removing these covariates substantially altered the model evidence (Bayes Factors) for several key hypotheses (e.g., H4, H5a-d, H9b,d), in some cases changing the substantive conclusion drawn from the model comparison. Specifically, the analysis without covariates provides strong evidence against a model predicting differences in learning between the experimental groups (H4: $BF_{01} > 100$). It favors a two-way interaction model predicting a uniform influence of confidence on belief updating across groups over a null model and over a more complex three-way interaction model (e.g. for the two-way interaction model compared to the null model; H5a, PSC: $BF_{10} > 100$; H5b, OCBS: $BF_{10} = 2.31$). Furthermore, it suggests that a three-way interaction model predicting an influence of reactance on OCBS updating, that is moderated by the experimental groups, represents our data the most, compared to a simpler two-way interaction model excluding the group interaction ($BF_{10} > 100$). This discrepancy in the results indicates that the covariates are integral to the model and not merely incidental controls. Their impact suggests that they are clarifying the respective relationships of interest by reducing error variance.

Therefore, this sensitivity analysis confirms the importance of their inclusion. The primary models reported in the main text, which include the selected covariates, are retained as a more unbiased and valid specification for testing our hypotheses.

Table A7

Bayesian Hypothesis Testing Results Without Covariates

Hypothesis	Description	Models Compared (M_1 vs. M_0)	BF_{10}
H1	Group moderates change in PSC (T1–T2).	Interaction vs. Main Effects	> 100
H2	Debriefing increases PSC in low group (T2–T3).	Time Effect vs. Intercept-Only	>100
H3	Knowledge (VW) increases from T1 to T2.	Time Effect vs. Intercept-Only	<0.01
H4	Group moderates change in knowledge (T1–T2).	Interaction vs. Main Effects	<0.01
H5a	Prior confidence moderates change in PSC.	2-Way Interaction vs. Base Model	>100
H5b	Prior confidence moderates change in CB.	2-Way Interaction vs. Base Model	2.31
H5c	Group alters the moderation effect on PSC.	3-Way Interaction vs. 2-Way Interaction	<0.01
H5d	Group alters the moderation effect on CB.	3-Way Interaction vs. 2-Way Interaction	<0.01
H6	Prior confidence moderates the debriefing effect.	Interaction vs. Main Effects	>100
H7	Initial climate belief predicts reactance.	Predictor Model vs. Intercept-Only	>100
H8	Political party affiliation predicts reactance.	Predictor Model vs. Intercept-Only	>100
H9a	Reactance moderates change in PSC.	2-Way Interaction vs. Base Model	>100
H9b	Reactance moderates change in CB.	2-Way Interaction vs. Base Model	>100
H9c	Group alters the moderation effect on PSC.	3-Way Moderation vs. 2-Way Interaction	>100
H9d	Group alters the moderation effect on CB.	3-Way Moderation vs. 2-Way Interaction	>100

Note. PSC = Perceived Scientific Consensus; VW = Factual Knowledge; CB = Climate Beliefs (aggregated score). BF_{10} represents the Bayes factor in favor of the alternative hypothesis model (M_1) over the null hypothesis model (M_0). A $BF_{10} > 3$ is considered moderate evidence and > 10 is strong evidence for M_1 . A $BF_{10} < 1/3$ is moderate evidence and $< 1/10$ is strong evidence for M_0 .

A8. Increase in Confidence After Receiving the Consensus Message

We conducted an exploratory analysis to see if the intervention affected confidence levels directly. This analysis revealed a significant increase in confidence in one's PSC scores across all conditions (from $M = 77.1\%$ at T1 to $M = 87.8\%$ at T2; mean increase = 10.7 percentage points, 95% CI [9.5, 11.9], $BF_{10} > 100$). The increase in confidence was significantly higher in the low and high groups compared to the control group ($BF_{10} > 100$; the increase was 8.8

percentage points larger in the low group, 95% CI [5.9, 11.6], and 10.0 percentage points larger in the high group, 95% CI [7.2, 12.6], compared to the control group). The difference in the increase between the low and high group was not credible (95% CI [-0.01, 0.04]). The mean change in confidence per group is illustrated in Figure A1.

Fig. A1. Mean Change in Confidence in Perceived Scientific Consensus by Groups

Note. The change score is the difference between post- and pre-consensus message Confidence in PSC. The “control” group only saw the climate video, the “low” group received the 55% consensus message + video, and the “high” group received the 97% consensus message + video. Error bars represent the 95% confidence interval.

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